

**SOCIAL WELFARE NEED OF AND CARE FOR INTERNALLY
DISPLACED PERSONS (IDPs) IN KUMBOTSO LOCAL GOVERNMENT
AREA, KANO STATE**

AN EMPERICAL PAPER PRESENTED

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Abstract

This study is titled Social Welfare Need of and Care for Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State. The study sought to identify the social welfare need of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), to examine the care regimen for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), and find out the Challenges facing care-givers of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State. The study adopted a survey research methodology in which a sample of two hundred and five (205) subjects from the population of six hundred and fifty eight (658) IDPs and Staff of Kumbotso Local Government Area was drawn. A self-developed multiple choice questionnaire and interview-guide were used by the researcher in collecting data. While the questionnaire answered the research questions one (1) and two (2) among the IDPs, the interview-guide answered the three (3) research questions among Local Government Staff. However, data was analyzed using simple frequency and percentages as well as qualitative analysis of the information. The findings of the study revealed that the social welfare needs of IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area were Security, Housing, Accommodation, Feeding, Medication, Clothing, Education, Empowerment, Job, and Repatriation. The care-regimen for IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area was provided by the Local Government Council and Volunteers in terms of social services provision. The challenges faced by the care-givers of IDPs in Kimbotso Local Government Area were inadequate facilities, low finances, poor communal participation, lack of civilization and awareness by the IDPs, and poor sustainability. The study recommends that the Local Government should collaborate with NEMA to secure funds and facility which will promote sustainability of the programme, the Local Government should create a committee of local proprietors that will actively contribute to the affairs of the IDPs, and the Local government should provide community mobilization through enlightenment of the general public to participate in the provision of assistance to the IDPs in the Local Government Area.

Introduction

As conflicts have been unavoidable throughout human civilization, displacement of people has become a major social problem which sets back modernization across the globe. For more than two decades, human civilization has witnessed many catastrophes that have resulted into the displacement of people across continents, countries, and states. For instance, the political up-rising in the Arabian countries at the 2000's had pushed the Arabs to migrate to different parts of Europe. In South America, countries like Mexico and Columbia have had a long history of the scourge of criminal gangs and large-scale military operations against them, also, and both of which have forced people from their homes. In regional terms, moreover, say in the African continent, sub-Saharan Africa, West Africa, and North Africa, in which countries like Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Sudan, and Central African Republic (CAR) are located, have been constituted with millions of internally displaced persons (IDPs) over the years. However, according to statistics, while there were still only 2.2 million IDPs in Europe, the Caucasus and Central Asia, there were more than 9.1 million IDPs in the Middle East and North Africa; the DRC's displaced population alone remained at nearly three million. Recently too, Nigeria give an official figure of IDPs for the first time, and which stood at 3.3 million (IDMC, 2014).

The phenomenon of insurgency in Nigeria has been evident since her independence in 1960, ranging from the twelve-day revolution by Adaka Boro (1964), to the Civil war (1967-1970), the Maitasine Saga (1980) in Kano, to the various ethnic disturbances by militias such as the O'odua People's Congress(OPC), the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), the Movement for the Emancipation of Niger Delta(MEND), and most recently, the Niger-Delta Avengers. However, the most devastating, by the "Ahl al sunnali al

alDa'wawa al Jihad", popularly known as Boko Haram, has been experienced in Northern Nigeria since early 2000, with its origin linked with the wide-spread socio-economic and religious insecurity among certain communities in the North, especially the North-East. The activities of this gang have unleashed terrible humanitarian crises in North East, Nigeria (Fwatshak and Larab, 2007; Ikelegbe, 2010). The continued increase in the spread of the destructive activities of the Boko Haram sect in North-East, Nigeria since 2009 has created adverse socio-economic consequences in the North-East region. Thus, life in the various communities of Borno, Yobe and Adamawa states, such as Kawuri, Baga, Konduga, Bama, Shuwa, Ajigin, Gamboru, Giwa, Chibok, Gwoza to mention a few, have been characteristically harsh, poverty-stricken and, most times, short (Salkida, 2012). In short, the region has ceased to know civil normalcy as a result of the dire humanitarian situation, as evident in the high incidence of human casualties, human rights abuses, population displacement and refugee debacle, loss of means of livelihood, food insecurity, limited medical facilities and many other social upheavals. Moreover, the increasing influx of refugees and the spill-over effect of Boko Haram violence into neighbouring countries, over the years, have resulted to serious regional security risks, despite the Joint Border Patrol Command to address the increasing security challenges attributable to the insurgency (This day, April 16th 2014).

However, in line with the concern of the administration in Nigeria for the security and welfare of the citizenry the progressive development of the nation, and the reduction, if not completely eradication of menace of internally displacement. It is with pleasure that the former President recommended to the general public, the first National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons in 2008. The adoption of the Policy has suffered delays, the consequence of which has denied the country a number of opportunities which it can access only when the policy is in

place. He further urged all tiers of government, non-governmental organizations, international partners, civil society and all stakeholders in the humanitarian field to give it wide publicity and to implement its provision faithfully and diligently. (Goodluck, 2008). In addition to this and in accordance to the promises made within the APC manifestations by the then presidential contestant and winning candidate as well, Muhammad Buhari thus; the administration will focus on internal security, fighting against bribery and corruption, and employment opportunities for the teeming youth.

During internal conflicts, displaced victims are usually confronted with a wide range of physical and psychological trauma to their persons coupled with loss of their homes and other life time investments. Consequently, Abduction, sexual slavery, forced recruitment and other major violations of human rights have affected thousands of women, children and their families (Nigeria: Protection Sector Factsheet, 2016). Moreover, according to the International Organization for Migration (2016) there are 2,241,484 Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria, as at February, 2016. Furthermore, according to the report, this figure is particularly based on an assessment conducted from November to December 2015 by the International Organization for Migration's Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) team in two hundred and seven (207) Local Government Areas covering the thirteen (13) States of Northern Nigeria. In fact, to complicate matters, as IDPs are returning to their habitual residences, others are still being displaced, thereby making it difficult to accurately establish reliable statistics of IDPs in Nigeria. As a result of the aforementioned, since 2011, the populations of the North-East of Nigeria have consistently been destabilized by the insurgency-related clashes between the Boko Haram and governmental forces (UNICEF, 2014). Perhaps being Kano State is the Focal point of the Northern part of Nigeria in terms of civilization, relationship, economy, population, and a

well inherent nature of acceptance and accommodation of people. For years many displaced persons from the North-East have migrated to Kano State in search of places to live and start a new beginning. One of the said local governments, from these thirteen (13) States in the Northern Nigeria, is Kumbotso Local Government Area of Kano State which has for long accommodated various IDPs from the North-Eastern parts of Nigeria. Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State, has been one of the semi-metropolitan local Governments in the State where many of these migrants have resettled. The mostly affected areas in the Kumbotso Local Government Area are Mariri, Naibawa, Panshekara, Bubbugaji, Sabuwar gandu, Sheka, and Danbare. The Local Government administration of Kumbotso local government area in Kano State adopted a Care-regimen programme for the IDPs found in the local government territory. This programme was designed to provide social welfare service to the IDPs so as to attain a satisfying standard of lives of the citizenry. Many of these IDPs are victims of the Boko Haram from the North-East who are vulnerable and need to be taking care by government, organizations, and individuals.

Statement of the problem

The displacement of people from their various communities has become a global phenomenon greatly disturbing governments, organizations, and individuals who have willingly to come to the defense of human civilization. For three decades, empirical studies have highlighted ethnic crises, religious conflicts, wars, and political uprisings, natural and man-made disasters which have led to the displacement of people within and outside their communities across the continents of the world. In the context of Nigeria, therefore, many people have been greatly suffering between State borders in the North-Eastern part of the country. In fact, since the inception of the Boko Haram insurgences, thousands of people across the region have been

massacred and their towns and villages destroyed. In addition, many schools and hospitals have been devastated as a result of the capture of towns by the militants. Legitimate market activities in the North-East have ceased and; women and their children have moved from their various communities. These, and many other problems, have necessitated the forced migration of people from their States of origin to the neighboring States, in search of security for their lives.

As such being already affected with the problem has gingered the Local Government authority of Kumbotso there into social interaction in favour of the IDPs. It was in the light of this, that this study appraised the social welfare need and care regimen for the IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

The objectives of the study are:

- i) To identify the social welfare need of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.
- ii) To examine the care regimen for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.
- iii) To find out the Challenges facing care-givers of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

This study will be guided by the following three questions, and they are:

- i) What is the social welfare need of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State?
- ii) What is the care regimen for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State?

- iii) What are the challenges facing care-givers of the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State?

Conceptual Clarifications

For the purpose of clarification here, the following concepts are defined based on their usage in the study:

Care - In this study refers to an art of showing concern for the lives of IDPs by government of Kumbotso in Kano State.

Care-givers - This refers to those officials and voluntary individuals who have actively participated in the provision of social welfare services to the IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

Care regimen - This is concerning the nature of programme designed by the Kumbotso Local Government Council aimed at alleviating the plight of the IDPs through the provision of social services in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

Internally displaced Persons (IDPs) - In this study, Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are those seeking-out vagrants from the North-Eastern part of Nigeria, due to the disturbing insurgences caused by Boko Haram militants in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

Social welfare need - This is regarded as the combination of needs and basic wants of the IDPs which has resulted from their displacement.

Methodology

Research design - This research employed a survey research methodology because it considered the population of the IDPs and Local Government Staff of Kumbotso Local Government as subjects of study.

Population - The population for the study encompasses the IDPs and staff of Kumbotso Local Government Area. According to the Community and Social Development Department of Kumbotso Local Government Council, the IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area were five hundred and sixty seven (567) while the staffs of the Local government Council in charge of them were ninety one (91). Therefore, the population for the study was six hundred and fifty eight (658) subjects.

Sample size - For the purpose of sampling, this study adopted the recommendation by the Research Advisers (2006) which require that for a population of five hundred and sixty seven (567) persons, one hundred and ninety six (196) subjects should be selected. In the case of the Staff of the Local Government, however, the study adopted the Gay's (2006) 10% formula for interview. Therefore, out of the ninety-one (91) Staff of Kumbotso Local Government only nine (9) were selected. In this study therefore, while the Staff were drawn purposively, the IDPs were selected through a simple random technique through which each one of them has the probability of being chosen to answer the questionnaire.

Instruments for data collection - The study employed the questionnaire and interviewing modes of data collection. Regarding the questionnaire, a self-developed multiple choice instrument was designed for the IDPs and named "Questionnaire for the IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area" (QIDPSKLG). This instrument sought for the demographic data of the

IDPs such as age, gender, marital status, educational background, and occupation as well as questions targeted at answering research question 1 and 2. However, the interview with the Staff of Kumbotso Local Government Area was conducted using a researcher-constructed interview-guide named “Interview Guide for the Staff of Kumbotso Local Government” (IGSKLG) and within which research questions 1, 2, and 3 were covered.

Method of data analysis - Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and simple percentages with interpretations while the data collected through the interview method were analyzed qualitatively.

Results Presentation and Data Analysis

Data in this study was analyzed using simple frequency counts and percentages. One hundred and ninety six (196) questionnaires were distributed to One hundred and ninety six (196) IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area. All the one hundred and ninety six questionnaires (196) were successfully retrieved. Moreover, the results of the interview with the Staffs of Kumbotso Local Government council will be incorporated into the discussions of findings from the questionnaires duly collected. The following tables presents data on demography of respondents and answers to research questions one (1) and two (2) in which n= 196 respectively.

Table 1.1 Demographic data of IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State

Variable	Options	Frequency	Percentage
i) Age	a) Below 19	75	38.2
	b) 19-34	56	28.6
	c) 35-49	46	23.5
	d) 50 and more	19	9.7
ii) Gender	a) Male	74	37.8
	b) Female	122	62.2
iii) Marital Status	a) Single	101	51.5
	b) Married	11	5.6
	c) Divorced	16	8.2
	d) Widowed	68	34.7
iv) Formal Education Background	a) Primary school	74	37.8
	b) Secondary	25	12.8
	c) Post-secondary	12	6.1
	d) Any other? Please specify: Islamiyya & Qur'anic schools	85	43.3
v) Occupation before displacement	a) Farming	42	21.4
	b) Trading	53	27.1
	c) Crafts	36	18.4
	d) Any other? Please specify: home mgt, laborer & pensioners	65	33.1
vi) Occupation now	a) Farming	0	00
	b) Trading	37	18.9
	c) Crafts	54	27.6
	d) Any other? Please specify: Nanny, drivers, laborers	105	53.5

Interpretation

The table above presents the demographic data of the respondents thus; age, gender, marital status, formal education background, occupation before displacement, and their present occupations. According to the table, respondents within the age category of below 19 years

constituted the highest number with 38.2%. This implies that most of the IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government were young people and children. In addition to this, those within the range of 19-34 constituted a sound number of 56 (28.6%) while respondents within the range of 35-49 were 46 (23.5%) the respondents 50 and above were 19 (9.7%). This means that respondents within the ages of 19-49 were highly energetic, and those above 50 were very small in number. However, the female respondents constituted 62.2% and their male counterparts with 37.8% which means that most of the IDPs were female. Accordingly, the respondents who are living without marriage have 51.5%. While divorced respondents were 16 (8.2%) the married ones were 11 (5.6) and widows were 68 (34.7%). This informs us that many of the IDPs lost their husbands and wives during the insurgences. From the educational background more so, the respondents who have attended primary school were 74 (37.8%), while those respondent who attended secondary school constituted 12.8%, the respondents who attended post-secondary education were very few with 6.1%. and huge sum of 85 (43.3%) have not being to formal school system, they have been to Islamiyya and Qua'anic schools. Furthermore, the occupation of the respondents before displacement included farming with 21.4% and trading 27.1%. While those engaged in crafts were 18.4%, those respondents with highest percentage of 33.1% were engaged in labour, domestic housewives and pensioners. And finally, the occupations engaged by the respondents currently shows that no IDPs engaged in farming and those who engaged in trading constituted 18.9%. While 54 (27.6%) were engaged in crafts activities, the highest number of 105 (53.5%) were engaged in labour, Nanny and driving in motor parks.

Table 1.2 The Social Welfare Need of Internally Displaced Person's (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

Variable	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1. What are your major requirements here?	a) Security	39	19.9
	b) Education	27	13.8
	c) Feeding	66	33.6
	d) Accommodation	33	16.8
	e) Empowerment	24	12.2
	f) Any other? Please specify: vocational skill & work	7	3.6
2. What other social welfare need will you recommend?	a) Clothing	44	22.4
	b) Repatriation	63	32.1
	c) Medication	21	10.7
	d) Housing	25	12.8
	e) Job	35	17.9
	f) Any other? Please specify: electrification	8	4.1
3. What social amenities do you miss here but provided in your home village/town?	a) Water	21	10.7
	b) School	111	56.6
	c) Transportation	11	5.6
	d) Hospital	43	21.9
	e) Any other? Please specify: recreational facility	10	5.1

Interpretation

From the above table which described the social welfare need of IDPs, the respondents who believed that security is their major requirement from the regimen were 39 (19.9%). While those who opined that education was their major requirement were 13.8%, the respondents who believed that feeding is their major requirement from the regimen were 66 (33.6%). Meaning that, most of the IDPs were suffered with Hunger. Moreover, the respondents who agreed that their major requirement from the regimen was accommodation were (16.8%) and those looking for empowerment as their major requirement constituted (12.2%) and those belonging to other category which include vocational skill acquisition as their major requirement from the regimen were (3.6%). In addition to this, the respondents who recommended that clothing is other social welfare need require from the regimen were 44 (22.4%). However, respondents who were recommending for repatriation as their major requirement from the regimen were 63 (32.1%). While the respondents recommending for medication as their major requirement from the regimen were (10.7%), the respondents recommending for housing as their major requirement from the regimen were (12.8%). And while only 8 (4.1%) belonging to other category who recommended that electrification as their major requirement from the regimen, (17.9%) recommended that getting job as their major requirement from the regimen. Furthermore, the respondents who believed that they missed water as social amenity which was provided in their homes were 10.7%. Other respondents who constituted the majority with 56.6% opined that they missed school as social amenity provided at their homes. While respondents (21.9%) believed that they missed hospital as social amenity provided at their homes, the respondents (5.6%) opined that they missed transportation as social amenity provided at their homes. And respondents belonging to other category who missed means of communication as social amenity provided at their homes constituted (5.1%).

Table 1.3 The care regimen for the Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

Variable	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1. How do you feel being an IDP?	a) Unhappy	101	51.5
	b) Alienated	29	14.8
	c) Isolated	15	7.7
	d) All of the above	44	22.4
	e) Any other? Please specify: all the same	7	3.6
2. How could your situation here be improved?	a) By providing adequate shelter	31	15.8
	b) By providing employment	46	23.5
	c) By providing education	49	25
	d) By providing vocational occupation	44	22.4
	e) Any other? Please specify: capacity building (money)	26	13.3
3. Is there adequate	a) Food?	Yes 78 No 118	Yes 39.8 No 60.2
	b) Mutual attention?	107 89	54.6 45.4
	c) Hygiene facilities?	49 147	25 75
	d) Schooling?	56 140	28.6 71.4
	e) Any other? Please specify: water	39 157	19.9 80.1
4. What is the attitude of care providers to you?	a) Professional	52	26.5
	b) Respectful	117	59.7
	c) Unconcern	13	6.6

	d) Rude	5	2.6
	e) Any other? Please specify: caring	9	4.6

Interpretation

Table 1.3 described the care regimen in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State. According to the table, respondents who were unhappy for been an IDP were 101 (51.1%). While those felt alienated for been an IDP were (14.8%), the respondents who felt isolated for been an IDP were (7.7%). A reasonable figure of 44 (22.4) felt unhappy, alienated, and isolated for been an IDP. And those belonging to other category (13.3%) felt all is the same, meaning that to be in their homes or among the IDPs is the same because they have lost everything. The respondents who believed that their situation could be improved by providing adequate shelter constituted (15.8%). While respondents who opined that their situation could be improved by providing employment were 46 (23.5%), the respondents on the opinion that their situation could be improved by providing education were 49 (25%). However, respondents who agreed that their situation could be improved by providing vocational skill were 44 (22.4%), and those belonging to other category who thought that their situation could be improved by providing capacity building and utilization in form of money were (13.3%). Moreover, when asked regarding the regimen, whether there was adequacy of food, the respondents 118 (60.2%) said No, and (39.8%) said Yes. While respondents who opined that there was adequacy of mutual attention constituted (54.6%) and those who did not agree were (45.4%), the respondents who believed that there was adequacy of hygiene facilities were (25%) and those who disagreed were (75%). More so, respondents who opined that there was adequacy of schooling were (28.6%) and those respondents (71.4%) did not agree that there was adequacy of schooling in the regimen. And

those belonging to other category (19.9%) opined that water is adequate and (80.1%) believed that water was not adequate. Furthermore, the respondents who opined that the attitude of care providers to the IDPs was professional constituted (26.5%). Those respondents (59.7%) believed that the attitude of care providers to the IDPs was respectful. While small number of 5 (2.6%) opined that the attitude of care providers to the IDPs was rude, respondents (6.6%) opined that the attitude of care providers to the IDPs was unconcern. Finally, those respondents (4.6) belonging to the other category, opined that the attitude of care providers to the IDPs was of caring during the regimen.

Summary of findings:

- i. The social welfare needs of IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area were Security, Housing, Accommodation, Feeding, Medication, Clothing, Education, Empowerment, Water, Transportation, Job, and Repatriation.
- ii. The care regimen for IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area was provided professionally, respectfully, and carefully by the Local Government Council and Volunteers in terms of social services provision.
- iii. The challenges faced by the care givers of IDPs in Kimbotso Local Government Area were inadequate facilities, low finances, poor communal participation, lack of civilization and awareness by the IDPs, and poor sustainability.

Discussion of Results:

The first finding of the study reveals that the social welfare need of IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area were Security, Housing, Accommodation, Feeding, Medication, Clothing, Education, Empowerment, Water, Transportation, Job, and Repatriation. These were

almost in congruence with those reported by Jalili and Olanrewaju (2016) “the needs of the displaced varies depending on their former status and intensity of their displacement, central to displaced persons are shelter, food and security. Meanwhile, it is expected that where shelter is provided, food and security should be provided which makes shelter paramount.”

In addition to this, according to the interview with the Kumbotso Local Government Staff, the social welfare need of IDPs was confirmed with those reported by the IDPs from the questionnaires. However, this need have become of vital significance to the lives of the IDPs.

The second finding of the study reveals that the care regimen for IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area was provided professionally, respectfully, and with care by the Local Government Council and Volunteers in terms of social services provision. Regarding this, agencies burdened with the management of displacements have been established to reflect more of social mending establishment rather than social preventing and recuperation (Jalili and Olanrewaju, 2016). More so, most of the children among the IDPs were enrolled in to Primary, Islamuyya and Qur’anic schools.

Finally, the last findings of the study which reveals the challenges faced by the care givers of IDPs in Kumbotso Local Government Area were inadequate facilities, low finances, poor communal participation, lack of civilization and awareness by the IDPs, and poor sustainability. Many responses during the interview justified that a serious challenge face by the care givers is the problem of lack of civilization and awareness of the IDPs. This was in contrast with the challenges reported in empirical studies by Eweka, O. and Olusegun, T. O, and Obikaeze, V.C. and Onuoha, C. B in 2016. These scholars added Corruption, Policies, Attitude of Host Community, Overlapping of IDPs Management Institutions, Lack of Communication,

Bad Terrain, and Unpreparedness among the challenges faced by care givers and institutions for the IDPs.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

Management for IDPs in Nigeria has become a necessity and it involves not only Government at various levels, it also involves non-governmental agencies, individual philanthropies as well as religious and tribal organizations in such a way to reduce the vulnerability in the IDPs across the Nation. Therefore there is the need for sustainable regimen for IDPs to be in place through effective institutionalized system.

This study recommends that the Local Government should collaborate with National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) or any other agency that was charged with taking care of the IDPs to secure funds and facility which will promote sustainability of the programme. The Local Government should create a committee of local proprietors that will actively contribute to the affairs of the IDPs, and the Local government should provide community mobilization through enlightenment of the general public to participate in the provision of assistance to the IDPs in the Local Government Area.

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**QUESTIONNAIRE FOR IDPS IN KUMBOTSO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA
(QIDPSKLG)**

Please tick (√) the appropriate choice of yours or fill in the spaces provided.

Section A: Demographic data of respondents

1. Age: a) below 19 ()
b) 19-34 ()
c) 35-49 ()
d) 50 and more ()

2. Gender: a) Male ()
b) Female ()

3. Marital Status: a) Single ()
b) Married ()
c) Divorced ()
d) Widowed ()

4. Formal Educational Background: a) Primary School ()
b) Secondary School ()
c) Post-secondary ()
d) Any other: Please specify.....

5. Occupation before displacement: a) Farming ()
b) Trading ()
c) Crafts ()
d) Any other? Please specify.....

6. Occupation now: a) Farming ()
b) Trading ()
c) Crafts ()
d) Any other? Please specify.....

Section B

1. For how long have you been here?
a) 4 years and more ()
b) 3 years ()

- c) 2 years ()
- d) 1 year ()
- e) Below a year ()
- 2. What is the state of your health?
 - a) Physically healthy ()
 - b) Mentally healthy ()
 - c) Physically impaired ()
 - d) Mentally deranged ()
 - e) Psychologically unfit ()
 - f) Any other? Please specify.....
- 3. What are your major requirements here?
 - a) Security ()
 - b) Education ()
 - c) Feeding ()
 - d) Accommodation ()
 - e) Empowerment ()
 - f) Any other? Please specify.....
- 4. What other social welfare need would you recommend?
 - a) Clothing ()
 - b) Repatriation ()
 - c) Medication ()
 - d) Housing ()
 - e) Job ()
 - f) Any other? Please specify.....
- 5. Should this care-regimen be sustained by the Kumbotso Local Government?
 - a) Yes ()
 - b) No ()
 - c) Undecided ()
- 6. What social amenities do you miss here but provided in your home village/town?
 - a) Water ()
 - b) School ()
 - c) Transportation ()
 - d) Hospital ()
 - e) Any other? Please specify.....
- 7. How do you feel being an IDP?
 - a) Unhappy ()
 - b) Alienated ()
 - c) Isolated ()
 - d) All of the above ()
 - e) Any other? Please specify.....
- 8. How could your situation here be improved?
 - a) By providing adequate shelter ()
 - b) By providing employment ()
 - c) By providing education ()
 - d) By providing vocational skill ()
 - e) Any other? Please specify.....

- | | Yes | No |
|--|-----|-----|
| 9. Is there adequate | | |
| a) Food? | () | () |
| b) Mutual attention? | () | () |
| c) Hygiene facilities? | () | () |
| d) Schooling? | () | () |
| e) Any other? Please specify..... | | |
| 10. What is the attitude of care providers to you? | | |
| a) Professional | | () |
| b) Respectful | | () |
| c) Unconcern | | () |
| d) Rude | | () |
| e) Any other? Please specify..... | | |
| 11. In your own point of view does this care regimen serve it purpose? | | |
| a) Yes | | () |
| b) No | | () |
| c) Undecided | | () |
| 12. What other recommendation can you make for the care regimen | | |
| | | |
| | | |
| | | |

Interview-guide for the Staff of Kumbotso Local Government Council (IGSKLG)

Sir,

- i) What is the nature of care you provide to IDPs? (Please be elaborate) on regimen and provision.
- ii) Can you state since when this care regimen started?
- iii) What is the major objective of the programme for IDPs?
- iv) Who sponsored the programme?
- v) Please summarize the perceived social welfare need of the IDPs?
- vi) A part from the Local Government Council, who are the other sponsors for the programme?
- vii) What are the major challenges you faced in caring for the IDPs?
- viii) Can you recommend further improvement in the care of the IDPs?
- ix) Suggest ways to sustain the programme in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.